

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DN4 AND LANSS CLINICAL SCALES IN DIAGNOSING DIABETIC NEUROPATHIC PAIN

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Abstract. Diabetic neuropathy is one of the most common and disabling complications of diabetes mellitus, occurring in 50-90% of patients depending on the duration of the disease and the degree of carbohydrate metabolism compensation. According to the International Diabetes Federation, the number of patients with diabetes mellitus worldwide will reach 700 million by 2045, making the problem of diabetic complications one of the priority areas of modern medicine. The painful form of diabetic neuropathy develops in 11-24% of patients with diabetes mellitus and is characterized by the development of chronic neuropathic pain syndrome, which significantly worsens the quality of life of patients. Neuropathic pain in diabetes is characterized by particular intensity and torment, manifesting as burning, shooting pains, allodynia, and hyperalgesia, primarily in the distal parts of the lower extremities. This type of pain responds poorly to traditional analgesics and requires specific therapy with anticonvulsants, antidepressants, and other medications that affect the mechanisms of neuropathic pain.

Keywords: diabetic neuropathy, neuropathic pain, DN4, LANSS, diabetes mellitus, diagnostic scales, pain syndrome, electroneuromyography, polyneuropathy, screening

Objective of the study: to assess the diagnostic value of DN4 and LANSS clinical scales in identifying neuropathic pain syndrome in patients with diabetes mellitus and to determine their role in optimizing therapeutic approaches.

Study subjects. The study included 52 patients with type 1 and 2 diabetes mellitus who were treated in the endocrinology department of City Clinical Hospital No. 1 and the consultative polyclinic of the Tashkent City Endocrinological Dispensary. Confirmed diagnosis of type 1 or 2 diabetes mellitus. Age from 25 to 70 years, duration of diabetes at least 5 years. Presence

of clinical signs of diabetic neuropathy. Pain syndrome in the feet and/or lower leg area lasting at least 3 months. Informed consent to participate in the study

Conclusions: A high prevalence of neuropathic pain was observed, with the neuropathic component of pain syndrome detected in 69.2-75.0% of patients with diabetic neuropathy, which confirms the need for targeted screening of this complication. The DN4 scale demonstrates higher sensitivity (89.7% vs. 84.6%) and specificity (84.6% vs. 76.9%) compared to LANSS in diagnosing diabetic neuropathic pain. A significant negative correlation was established between the indicators of both scales and the nerve fiber conduction velocity (r from -0.59 to -0.71, $p < 0.001$), which confirms their validity in diabetic neuropathy.

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